

Computational Detection of Text Reuse in the Chinese Buddhist Canon

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Abstract

This paper presents the first corpus-wide computational analysis of text reuse in the Taishō Tripiṭaka (大正新脩大藏經 *Dàzhèng xīnxiū dàzàngjīng*), the standard modern edition of the Chinese Buddhist canon containing approximately 2,920 texts across 85 volumes. Using a five-stage pipeline (text extraction, n-gram fingerprinting, seed-and-extend alignment, scoring, and classification), I detected 3,610 significant textual relationships involving 1,558 unique texts. These include 135 excerpts (texts $\geq 80\%$ derived from a single source), 539 digests (30–80% derived), 538 commentaries, 224 retranslations, and 2,174 shared-tradition pairs. The pipeline was validated against the well-established derivation of the Heart Sūtra from the Large *Prajñāpāramitā*, correctly classifying all six test cases. Notable discoveries include the systematic quantification of encyclopedic absorption (e.g., the 法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín*, “Forest of Gems in the Garden of the Dharma,” incorporates 102 shorter texts at measurable coverage levels), the comprehensive mapping of dhāraṇī derivation networks, and the detection of a 28.6-percentage-point gap between same-translator and cross-translator matching: a computational signature of translator individuality previously described only qualitatively. A phonetic transliteration detection module identifies 270 text pairs with phonetically equivalent passages where different Chinese characters encode the same Sanskrit sounds. Independent validation using a unified Taishō–Tibetan concordance confirms 93.6% of computationally detected retranslation pairs when both texts have Tibetan parallel data.

Keywords: Chinese Buddhist canon; Taishō; text reuse; digest texts; computational philology; dhāraṇī; transliteration

1 Introduction

The Chinese Buddhist canon is one of the world’s largest premodern literary corpora. The Taishō Tripiṭaka (大正新脩大藏經 *Dàzhèng xīnxiū dàzàngjīng*), published between 1924 and 1934 under the editorship of Takakusu Junjirō (高楠順次郎) and Watanabe Kaigyoku (渡辺海旭), represents the most comprehensive modern critical edition of the Chinese Buddhist canon. Its 85 volumes and approximately 2,920 texts span more than a millennium of translation, compilation, and indigenous composition, from the earliest translations attributed to An Shigao (安世高 *Ānshìgāo*, fl. 148–170 CE) to Song-dynasty and later works. The CBETA project (中華電子佛典協會 *Zhōnghuá diànzǐ fōdiǎn xiéhuì*, Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association) has digitized the full canon in TEI P5b XML format (CBETA 2024), making corpus-scale computational analysis possible for the first time.

Among the defining features of this literary tradition is the pervasive reuse of textual material: shorter texts are extracted from longer ones, encyclopedic compilations absorb earlier works

wholesale, different translators render the same Indic source in different Chinese, and commentators weave source quotations into original exegesis. Despite the centrality of text reuse to Chinese Buddhist literary culture, no previous study has attempted to detect and classify these relationships computationally across the full canon. Individual text-critical studies have analyzed specific cases, most notably Jan Nattier’s demonstration that the Heart Sūtra is a “digest” extracted from the Large *Prajñāpāramitā* (Nattier 1992), but the comprehensive, corpus-wide approach remains unexplored.

This paper presents an automated five-stage pipeline that analyzes all 8,982 XML files in the CBETA corpus and detects textual relationships based on character-level overlap, supplemented by phonetic transliteration matching for dhāraṇī and mantra passages. The pipeline detected 3,610 significant relationships involving 1,558 unique texts (roughly 63% of the extractable corpus), classified into five categories: excerpts, digests, retranslations, commentaries, and shared tradition.

The specific contributions of this paper are:

1. The first corpus-wide computational detection and classification of text reuse across the full Taishō canon.
2. A phonetic transliteration detection module that identifies cross-transliterator relationships in dhāraṇī and mantra literature, the first such module applied at corpus scale.
3. Systematic quantification of encyclopedic absorption: how Tang-dynasty compilations incorporated hundreds of earlier texts at measurable coverage levels.
4. Comprehensive mapping of derivation networks within dhāraṇī literature and Vinaya traditions.
5. Measurement of a 28.6-percentage-point translator-specific matching differential, providing a computational signature of translator individuality.
6. Independent validation via a Tibetan parallel concordance, confirming 93.6% of detected retranslation pairs.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant background in Buddhist Studies and computational text-reuse detection. Section 3 describes the five-stage pipeline methodology. Section 4 validates the pipeline against the Heart Sūtra test case. Section 5 presents the full corpus results. Sections 6 and 7 discuss the findings and their limitations. Section 8 outlines future directions, and Section 9 concludes.

2 Background

2.1 Text Reuse in the Chinese Buddhist Canon

Nattier’s landmark study (Nattier 1992) established the category of the “digest text” (抄經 *chāo-jīng*): a shorter work whose content is substantially derived from a longer source through selective extraction. Nattier demonstrated that the Heart Sūtra (*Prajñāpāramitāhṛdaya*; T251, 般若波羅蜜多心經 *Bōrě bōluómìduō xīnjīng*) was composed by extracting passages from Kumārajīva’s Chinese translation of the *Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā* (T223, 摩訶般若波羅蜜經 *Móhē bōrě bōluómì jīng*) and framing them with an original narrative apparatus: an opening scene featuring Avalokiteśvara, connective passages, a dhāraṇī, and a declaration of the teaching’s soteriological power.

While the Heart Sūtra case has received extensive scholarly attention (cf. Attwood 2021; Shi Huifeng 2014; Silk 1994), the broader phenomenon of digest composition in the Chinese canon has not been systematically studied. Medieval Chinese Buddhist bibliographers were well aware of the practice: the 開元釋教錄 *Kāiyuán shìjiào lù* (“Record of Buddhist Teachings of

the Kaiyuan Era,” T2154), compiled by Zhisheng (智昇 *Zhìshēng*) in 730 CE, carefully distinguished between translations, indigenous compositions, and compilations. Yet no modern study has attempted to identify and quantify digest relationships across the full canon.

2.2 Computational Approaches to Buddhist Texts

Computational text analysis has been applied to Buddhist corpora in several domains. Bingenheimer and colleagues have developed digital comparative catalogs for Āgama literature (Bingenheimer 2006). SuttaCentral maintains a database of cross-canon parallels across Pāli, Chinese, and Tibetan sources (Sujato and Brahmali 2024). The CBETA project has digitized the full Chinese canon in TEI XML format (CBETA 2024). The SAT Daizōkyō Text Database at the University of Tokyo provides full-text search and linked data integration for the Taishō corpus (University of Tokyo 2024).

For the Pāli canon, the present author has applied frequency-based text mining to identify textual strata (Zigmond 2021). For Chinese texts, Bingenheimer and colleagues have explored social network visualization of Buddhist biographical collections (Bingenheimer et al. 2011), and various studies have applied statistical methods to authorship attribution problems in Buddhist literature.

However, no previous work has applied corpus-wide text-reuse detection methods to the Chinese Buddhist canon. The present study fills this gap.

2.3 Computational Text Reuse Beyond Buddhist Studies

The detection of text reuse in large historical corpora has emerged as a significant subfield of digital humanities. The present approach draws on several established methodological traditions while addressing challenges specific to Chinese textual corpora.

The most comprehensive framework for historical text-reuse detection is Büchler’s TRACER system (Büchler et al. 2014), which provides a modular pipeline for detecting reuse at multiple levels of granularity, from verbatim quotation to loose paraphrase. TRACER segments texts, computes fingerprints, selects candidate pairs, performs detailed alignment, and scores the results. The present pipeline follows a broadly analogous architecture (fingerprinting, candidate selection, seed-and-extend alignment, scoring), though adapted for the specific characteristics of Chinese Buddhist texts.

Smith, Cordell, and Mullen (Smith et al. 2015) applied n-gram shingling and locality-sensitive hashing to detect reprinted texts across millions of nineteenth-century American newspaper pages. Their work demonstrated that efficient fingerprinting methods could scale to very large corpora while maintaining acceptable precision. The use of character 5-gram fingerprints with stop-gram filtering in the present pipeline follows a similar logic, though at a smaller corpus scale and with character-level rather than word-level n-grams.

For classical-language corpora, Forstall et al. (2015) developed enhanced word-level n-gram matching methods for detecting intertextuality in Latin poetry, emphasizing the importance of frequency-based weighting to distinguish meaningful allusions from common vocabulary. Bamman and Crane (Bamman and Crane 2008) applied similar methods to detect allusion in Latin prose, focusing on the distinction between direct quotation and more diffuse forms of textual dependence. Ganascia and colleagues (Ganascia et al. 2014) extended text-reuse detection to French literary texts, demonstrating its applicability to vernacular literary traditions.

These projects share a common methodological core (fingerprinting, candidate selection, alignment) but they operate on alphabetic scripts where “words” are readily tokenized by whites-

pace. Chinese text-reuse detection presents distinctive challenges. Chinese lacks word boundaries, so n-gram computation must operate at the character level. Each Chinese character carries roughly the semantic weight of an English morpheme: a 5-character n-gram corresponds approximately to a 5-word phrase in English, making character 5-grams substantially more specific than word 5-grams in alphabetic scripts (Lee 2007). The logographic writing system also means that transliterations of the same Sanskrit phoneme may use entirely different characters across translators (e.g., 竭 *jié* vs. 揭 *jiē* for Sanskrit ग *ga*), a problem with no analogue in alphabet-to-alphabet text reuse.

The present pipeline addresses these Chinese-specific challenges through three departures from the standard alphabetic-script approach: (1) character-level n-grams rather than word-level, with a size ($n = 5$) chosen to balance specificity against resilience to scribal variation; (2) a seed-and-extend alignment strategy adapted from the paradigm widely used in bioinformatics, which accommodates the minor character substitutions and insertions common in manuscript transmission; and (3) a phonetic transliteration detection layer that maps characters to canonical Sanskrit syllables, enabling the detection of cross-transliterator relationships invisible to any character-level method.

3 Methodology

The analysis proceeded through five sequential stages (Figure 1). All parameters are listed in Appendix A.

3.1 Stage 1: Text Extraction

All 8,982 XML files in the CBETA TEI P5b corpus were parsed, extracting Chinese text content while respecting TEI conventions. Character declaration tables (`charDecl`) were used to normalize variant characters, with priority given to normalized forms over Unicode mappings. Editorial apparatus was handled by preferring lemma readings (`<lem>`) over variant readings (`<rdg>`). Paratextual elements (notes, bylines, document numbers, fascicle markers) were excluded. Where present, the distinction between preface (序, *xù*) and sūtra body (經, *jīng*) sections was preserved.

After extraction and filtering of texts shorter than 20 Chinese characters (likely fragments), the corpus contained 2,455 texts.

3.2 Stage 2: Candidate Generation

Rather than performing $O(n^2)$ pairwise comparisons across all texts, I used character n-gram fingerprinting (Forstall et al. 2015; Smith et al. 2015) to identify candidate pairs efficiently.

N-gram size. I used 5-character n-grams, chosen by evaluating $n \in \{3, 4, 5, 6\}$ on the Heart Sūtra validation case. At $n = 3$, excessive false positives arose from common Buddhist terms only 3–4 characters long (e.g., 菩薩 *púsà*, “bodhisattva”; 波羅蜜 *bōluómì*, “*pāramitā*”); at $n = 6$, minor scribal variants and editorial differences broke matching chains, reducing T250→T223 coverage from 73% to 61%. The value $n = 5$ gave the best balance.

Stop-gram filtering. To prevent false positives from formulaic Buddhist stock phrases, I excluded 5-grams appearing in more than 5% of all documents (i.e., in more than 122 of the 2,455

Figure 1: Pipeline overview. Runtimes are for a full (uncached) run on consumer hardware. Stages 1, 4, and 5 together account for less than 1% of total runtime; the computational cost is dominated by candidate generation (Stage 2) and alignment (Stage 3).

texts). This removed 381 stop-grams. The most common are the formulaic openings and technical terms that make Buddhist texts *sound* similar without indicating direct textual relationship: 如是我聞一 *rúshì wǒ wén yī* (“Thus have I heard: at one [time]...”, appearing in 693 texts), 菩薩摩訶薩 *púsà móhēsà* (“bodhisattva mahāsattva,” 726 texts), and 阿耨多羅三 *ānòuduōluó sān* (a transliteration of Sanskrit *anuttara-sam-*, the opening of “supreme perfect [enlightenment],” 580 texts).

Containment metric. For each candidate pair, I computed a containment similarity: the fraction of the shorter text’s 5-grams present in the longer text. I chose containment over Jaccard similarity because the digest detection problem is inherently asymmetric: a 300-character text that is 70% drawn from a 300,000-character source has high containment but negligible Jaccard, and it is the containment that matters for identifying the relationship. A minimum containment threshold of 0.10 was imposed. A size ratio filter required the putative source to be at least $2\times$ the length of the putative digest, ensuring that the pipeline distinguishes digest relationships (short text from a long source) from retranslations (two texts of comparable length). Texts longer than 50,000 characters were excluded as unlikely digest candidates.

Performance. The candidate generation stage achieves its efficiency through set intersection: each text’s non-stopgram 5-grams are stored as a `frozenset` of hash values, and candidate pairs are identified by computing the intersection of these sets directly in Python’s compiled C runtime, rather than building a memory-intensive inverted index that maps every n-gram to its containing texts. Combined with binary search prefiltering by text size, Stage 2 processes the full 2,455-text corpus in approximately 23 minutes on consumer hardware (Apple M3, 8-core, 16 GB), dominated by n-gram set construction.

Stage 3 is the most computationally expensive step (30 minutes), because it performs detailed character-level alignment for each of the 13,528 candidate pairs identified by Stage 2. For a long source text like T223 (285,968 characters), the pipeline must build a complete hash table of all 5-character substrings, scan the full digest text against it, extend every seed match with a scoring algorithm, and then solve an optimal chaining problem, repeating this process for every candidate pair involving that source. Three performance-critical inner loops were therefore reimplemented in Cython (compiled to C): n-gram hashing (Stage 2), seed finding, and fuzzy extension (both Stage 3). These avoid per-character Python object overhead by operating directly on C-level Unicode code points, yielding 10–50× speedups over the equivalent pure-Python implementations.

Table 1 gives per-stage timings for a full (uncached) run. The computational cost is dominated by Stages 2 and 3, which together account for over 99% of total runtime.

Table 1: Per-stage runtimes (full uncached run, Apple M3, 8-core, 16 GB, 4 workers).

Stage	Operation	Time
1	Text extraction (8,982 XML files)	19 s
2a	N-gram candidate generation	23 min
2b	Phonetic candidate generation	36 s
3	Seed-and-extend alignment (13,528 pairs)	30 min
4	Scoring & classification	<1 s
5	Report generation	8 s
Total		~54 min

3.3 Stage 2b: Phonetic Candidate Generation

Character-level matching cannot detect relationships between texts that transliterate the same Sanskrit content using different Chinese characters, a common phenomenon when different translators render dhāraṇī, mantra, or proper names. To address this, I added a phonetic transliteration detection stage.

A character-to-syllable mapping table was derived from the Digital Dictionary of Buddhism (Muller 2024), extracting 559 Chinese characters used for Sanskrit transliteration, grouped into approximately 200 canonical syllable classes. Characters representing the same Sanskrit syllable (e.g., 竭 *jié* and 揭 *jiē*, both rendering Sanskrit ऋ *ga*) are treated as phonetically equivalent. To limit ambiguity, 26 characters mapping to more than 5 distinct syllables were excluded: because these characters can represent so many different Sanskrit sounds, including them would produce spurious matches between unrelated transliterations. The most polysemous are 婆 *pó* (21 readings), 波 *bō* (13), 摩 *mó* (12), and 羅 *luó* (12).

Transliteration regions within each text were identified from two sources: (1) XML-annotated dhāraṇī ranges in the CBETA TEI markup, and (2) density-based detection of regions where transliteration characters cluster. Syllable 3-gram fingerprints (rather than the 5-grams

used for character-level matching) were computed for each text’s transliteration regions; the shorter n-gram size reflects the fact that dhāraṇī passages are typically much shorter than prose texts, so longer n-grams would miss valid matches. Containment similarity was computed between pairs, requiring a minimum phonetic containment of 0.25.

This stage generated 6,850 candidate pairs (51% of all candidates).

3.4 Stage 3: Detailed Alignment

For each candidate pair, a seed-and-extend alignment was performed in five steps (Figure 2).

1. **Seed finding.** A hash table of all 5-character substrings in the source text was built. The digest text was scanned left to right; at each position where a 5-gram matched the source, the match was greedily extended character-by-character to find the longest exact match.
2. **Fuzzy extension.** Each seed boundary was extended with a scoring algorithm (+1 for match, -2 for mismatch, -2 for single-character gap), terminating when the cumulative score dropped below -4.
3. **Optimal chaining.** An interval scheduling algorithm selected the non-overlapping subset of seeds maximizing total digest coverage via dynamic programming.
4. **Segmentation.** The chained seeds partitioned the digest into alternating “matched” and “novel” segments.
5. **Phonetic rescan.** Each novel segment was rescanned for phonetically equivalent matches in the source, using the character-to-syllable table from Stage 2b. Seeds required at least 5 consecutive phonetically equivalent characters with at least 2 differing characters.

3.5 Stage 4: Scoring and Classification

Each aligned pair was scored on six dimensions: coverage (weight 0.35), longest matched segment (0.20), document number cross-reference (0.15), number of distinct source regions (0.10), length asymmetry (0.10), and average segment length (0.10). Classification followed a decision tree (Table 2):

Table 2: Classification rules.

Condition	Classification
Coverage < 10%	No relationship
Coverage 10–30%	Shared tradition
Coverage ≥ 30%, size ratio < 3.0	Retranslation
Coverage ≥ 80%, avg segment ≥ 15 chars	Excerpt
Coverage ≥ 30%, avg segment ≥ 10 chars	Digest
Coverage ≥ 30%, avg segment < 10 chars	Commentary

The size ratio test fires first for texts of comparable length: when the source is less than $3 \times$ the digest length and coverage exceeds 30%, the pair is classified as a retranslation rather than a digest. The full decision logic is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Seed-and-extend alignment process. (a) Exact 5-gram seeds are found between the source and digest. (b) Each seed is extended with fuzzy matching (+1 match, -2 mismatch/gap, terminating at -4). (c) An interval scheduling algorithm selects the non-overlapping subset maximizing coverage; overlapping seeds are rejected. (d) The digest is segmented into matched and novel regions. (e) Novel regions are rescanned for phonetic equivalences using the character-to-syllable table.

4 Validation: The Heart Sūtra Test Case

The pipeline was validated against the most well-studied digest relationship in the Chinese Buddhist canon: the derivation of the Heart Sūtra from the Large *Prajñāpāramitā*. All six validation assertions passed (Table 3).

Table 3: Heart Sūtra validation results.

Test	Expected	Actual	Status
T250 \rightarrow T223 classification	digest	digest	PASS
T250 \rightarrow T223 coverage	≥ 0.70	0.732	PASS
T251 jing \rightarrow T223 classification	digest	digest	PASS
T251 jing \rightarrow T223 coverage	≥ 0.30	0.446	PASS
T250 not digest of T251	not excerpt/digest	retranslation	PASS
T251 not digest of T250	not excerpt/digest	no relationship	PASS

The T250 result (73.2% coverage, 8 distinct source regions, longest segment of 156 characters) corresponds closely to the textual structure described by Nattier: the matched material is the doctrinal core drawn from the *Prajñāpāramitā*, while the 26.8% novel fraction corresponds to the narrative framing, connective tissue, and dhāraṇī.

Figure 3: Classification decision tree. Coverage is the fraction of the shorter text’s characters matched in the longer text. Size ratio is the length of the source divided by the length of the digest. Average segment length (avg seg) is the mean length of matched segments in characters.

The T251 result (44.6% coverage) is lower because Xuanzang’s phrasing differs systematically from Kumārājīva’s T223. This cross-translator gap (73% vs. 45%) is itself an important finding, discussed in §6.1.

To investigate whether the novel material in T250 and T251 might derive from other texts, I searched all novel segments across the full corpus. Neither text’s novel material is traceable, at the pipeline’s character-matching threshold, to any other extant text in the Taishō. The matched material is the doctrinal core; the novel material is precisely the apparatus a compiler would need to create a standalone sūtra from extracted philosophical material: an opening scene, connective tissue, a dhāraṇī, and a power attribution. This structural pattern is consistent with Nattier’s Chinese-composition hypothesis (Nattier 1992).

5 Results

5.1 Relationship Distribution

The pipeline detected 3,610 significant textual relationships (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of detected relationships.

Classification	Count	Percentage
Shared tradition	2,174	60.2%
Digest	539	14.9%
Commentary	538	14.9%
Retranslation	224	6.2%
Excerpt	135	3.7%
Total	3,610	100%

Excluding the shared tradition category (10–30% overlap, insufficient to indicate direct derivation), the pipeline found 1,436 higher-confidence relationships. Additionally, 57 multi-source digests were identified, texts drawing content from two or more distinct source texts.

5.2 Encyclopedic Absorption

The most striking pattern concerns three Tang-dynasty encyclopedic compilations that appear as source texts for dozens of shorter works (Table 5).

Table 5: Top 10 source texts by number of excerpt and digest relationships.

Source Text	Title	Derivatives
T53n2122	法苑珠林 <i>Fǎyuàn zhūlín</i>	102
T53n2121	經律異相 <i>Jīnglǜ yìxiàng</i>	48
T54n2123	諸經要集 <i>Zhūjīng yàojí</i>	28
T48n2016	宗鏡錄 <i>Zōngjìnglù</i>	24
T21n1336	陀羅尼雜集 <i>Tuóluóní zájí</i>	16
T18n0901	陀羅尼集經 <i>Tuóluóní jíjīng</i>	13
T22n1428	四分律 <i>Sifēnlǜ</i>	11
T51n2076	景德傳燈錄 <i>Jǐngdé chuándēnglù</i>	8
T02n0125	增壹阿含經 <i>Zēngyī āhánjīng</i>	8
T30n1579	瑜伽師地論 <i>Yúqié shīdì lùn</i>	7

- **法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín* (T53n2122)**: 102 digest relationships, including 11 at >80% coverage (verbatim excerpts) and 91 digests. This 100-fascicle compilation by Daoshi (道世 *Dàoshì*, d. 683) incorporates earlier sūtras wholesale.
- **經律異相 *Jīnglǜ yìxiàng* (“Illustrations of the Sūtras and Vinaya,” T53n2121)**: 48 digest relationships. Compiled by Baochang (寶唱 *Bǎochàng*) in 516 CE.
- **諸經要集 *Zhūjīng yàojí* (“Essential Collection from the Sūtras,” T54n2123)**: 28 digest relationships. Daoshi’s companion to the 法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín*.

That encyclopedic compilations quote earlier works is known. What is new is the systematic quantification: which texts are fully absorbed as excerpts (coverage approaching 100%), which are partially absorbed, and which are only lightly drawn upon. Table 6 lists the twenty texts most fully absorbed by the 法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín*.

Table 6: Top 20 texts absorbed by T53n2122 (法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín*), by coverage.

Taishō	Title	Coverage	Class
T15n0615	菩薩訶色欲法經 <i>Púsà hē sèyù fǎ jīng</i>	100.0%	excerpt
T12n0332	佛說優填王經 <i>Fóshuō Yōutiánwáng jīng</i>	99.4%	excerpt
T32n1689	請寶頭盧法 <i>Qǐng Bǐntóulú fǎ</i>	99.4%	excerpt
T02n0115	佛說馬有八態譬人經 <i>Fóshuō mǎ yǒu bā tài pì rén jīng</i>	98.3%	excerpt
T14n0494	阿難七夢經 <i>Ānán qī mèng jīng</i>	88.6%	excerpt
T12n0369	阿彌陀佛說呪 <i>Āmítuó fó shuō zhòu</i>	87.4%	excerpt
T17n0724	佛說罪業應報教化地獄經 <i>Fóshuō zuìyè yìngbào jiàohuà dìyù jīng</i>	84.3%	excerpt
T54n2123	諸經要集 <i>Zhūjīng yàojí</i>	84.0%	excerpt
T19n1028A	佛說護諸童子陀羅尼經 <i>Fóshuō hù zhū tóngzǐ tuóluóní jīng</i>	82.2%	excerpt
T02n0132a	佛說食施獲五福報經 <i>Fóshuō shíshī huò wǔ fúbào jīng</i>	82.0%	excerpt
T14n0581	佛說八師經 <i>Fóshuō bāshī jīng</i>	81.2%	excerpt
T14n0571	佛說婦人遇辜經 <i>Fóshuō fùrén yù gū jīng</i>	78.0%	digest
T16n0703	燈指因緣經 <i>Dēngzhǐ yīnyuán jīng</i>	77.0%	digest
T17n0805	佛說栴檀樹經 <i>Fóshuō zhāntán shù jīng</i>	76.4%	digest
T12n0370	阿彌陀鼓音聲王陀羅尼經 <i>Āmítuó gǔ yīnshēng wáng tuóluóní jīng</i>	74.4%	digest
T17n0751a	佛說五無反復經 <i>Fóshuō wǔ wú fǎnfù jīng</i>	73.4%	digest
T14n0551	佛說摩鄧女經 <i>Fóshuō Módèng nǚ jīng</i>	68.6%	digest
T14n0506	犍陀國王經 <i>Jiánduó guówáng jīng</i>	65.5%	digest
T51n2082	冥報記 <i>Míngbào jì</i>	65.3%	digest
T12n0395	佛說當來變經 <i>Fóshuō dānglái biàn jīng</i>	64.5%	digest

The coverage distribution across the three encyclopedias reveals distinct compilation strategies. Of T53n2122’s 102 absorbed texts, 11 (10.8%) are excerpts at >80% coverage and 91 (89.2%) are digests at 30–80%. T53n2121 (經律異相 *Jīnglǜ yìxiàng*) shows a similar pattern: 2 excerpts, 46 digests. The two encyclopedias also share 22 absorbed texts in common, including T14n0506, T17n0805, T03n0174, and T14n0510, indicating that the compilers drew from overlapping but non-identical portions of the available canon.

A question that the pipeline can raise but not resolve is directionality. When Daoshi’s 法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín* and a short independent sūtra share 99% of the shorter text’s content, did Daoshi copy the sūtra, or is the “sūtra” a later extract from the encyclopedia? For texts with established dating (such as the 菩薩訶色欲法經 *Púsà hē sèyù fǎ jīng*, attributed to the Eastern Jin dynasty, 317–420 CE, well before Daoshi), the direction is clear. For undated texts, the pipeline’s coverage data provides evidence but not a definitive answer.

5.3 Āgama Extracts

Several short independent sūtras were found to be verbatim excerpts of passages within the larger Āgama collections. The 佛為年少比丘說正事經 *Fó wèi niánshào bīqiū shuō zhèngshì jīng* (T14n0502, “Sūtra of the Buddha’s Teaching to a Young Monk on Right Conduct”) is 100% contained within the *Samyuktāgama* (T02n0099), as are T14n0503 (100%) and T14n0499 (100%). These results confirm what text-critical scholars have long suspected: many small in-

dependent sūtras in Taishō volumes 1–17 are individual discourse excerpts that were at some point separated from their Āgama context and transmitted independently.

5.4 Dhāraṇī Derivation Networks

The 陀羅尼雜集 *Tuólúóní zájí* (T21n1336, “Miscellaneous Dhāraṇī Collection”) functions as a reservoir text for dhāraṇī literature: 16 shorter texts were found to be excerpts, digests, or retranlations, with coverage ranging from 100% down to 43%. Similarly, the 陀羅尼集經 *Tuólúóní jíjīng* (T18n0901, “Dhāraṇī Collection Sūtra”) serves as a source for 13 shorter ritual and dhāraṇī texts.

This systematic mapping of dhāraṇī derivation networks appears to be a novel contribution. While individual dhāraṇī texts have been studied in relation to their sources, the comprehensive identification of which collections served as “parent” repositories has not been previously published.

5.5 Vinaya Derivation

The 四分律 *Sīfēnlǜ* (“Four-Part Vinaya,” T22n1428, *Dharmaguptaka*) serves as the source for an extensive network of derivative texts: the 四分比丘尼戒本 *Sīfēn bǐqiūní jièběn* (“Bhikṣuṇī Precepts,” T22n1431, 81.0%), the 四分尼羯磨 *Sīfēn ní jiémó* (“Bhikṣuṇī *Karmavācanā*,” T22n1434, 65.6%), the 四分僧戒本 *Sīfēn sēng jièběn* (“Bhikṣu Precepts,” T22n1429, 65.6%), and others. Similarly, the *Mūlasarvāstivāda* Vinaya (根本說一切有部毘奈耶 *Gēnběn shuō yīqiè yǒu bù pínàiyé*, T23n1442–1443) generates its own derivative network. The pipeline maps these full derivation networks in a way not previously quantified computationally.

5.6 Verse Digests of Prose Treatises

Among the highest-confidence results are verse summaries extracted from parent prose treatises. The *Abhidharmakośa* verses (T29n1560) are 99.5% contained in the prose commentary (T29n1558); the 辯中邊論頌 *Biànzhōngbiān lùnsòng* (T31n1601, “Verses Distinguishing the Middle from the Extremes”) are 99.7% contained in T31n1600 (treatise). While these relationships are well known, the pipeline’s ability to detect and quantify them validates the methodology.

5.7 Yogācāra Derivation Chain

The *Yogācārabhūmi* (瑜伽師地論 *Yúqíe shīdì lùn*, “Treatise on the Stages of Yoga Practice,” T30n1579), attributed to Asaṅga and translated by Xuanzang in 648 CE, is the foundational scholastic text of the Yogācāra tradition. At roughly 300,000 characters across 100 fascicles, it is one of the longest texts in the Taishō. The pipeline reveals it as a generative source for a substantial network of derivative texts, quantifying for the first time the degree to which later Yogācāra literature is textually embedded in this single treatise.

The highest-coverage derivative is 大乘稻芊經隨聽疏決 *Dàchéng dàogān jīng suítīng shū jué* (T85n2783), at 97.3% coverage, essentially a verbatim excerpt. The 菩薩戒本 *Púsà jiè běn* (“Bodhisattva Precepts,” T24n1501) shows 97.0% coverage with nearly 7,000 consecutive matching characters, confirming its well-known derivation from the precepts chapter of the *Yogācārabhūmi*. The 解深密經 *Jiěshēnmì jīng* (“Sūtra Unravelling the Thought,” *Samdhinirmocana*, T16n0676) matches at 86.5%, reflecting the extensive doctrinal passages shared

between the sūtra and the treatise. Further derivatives include the 菩薩戒羯磨文 *Púsà jiè jiémó wén* (“Bodhisattva Precepts *Karmavācanā*,” T24n1499) at 72.3%, the 佛為優填王說王法正論經 *Fó wèi Yōutiánwáng shuō wángfǎ zhènglùn jīng* (T14n0524) at 65.7%, and the 王法正理論 *Wángfǎ zhènglǐ lùn* (“Treatise on Right Principles of Governance,” T31n1615) at 62.9%.

Particularly notable is a two-stage derivation chain. The 顯揚聖教論 *Xiǎnyáng shèngjiào lùn* (“Treatise Elucidating the Holy Teachings,” T31n1602), itself 40.8% derived from the *Yogācārabhūmi*, in turn serves as the source for the 顯揚聖教論頌 *Xiǎnyáng shèngjiào lùnsòng* (“Verses of the Treatise Elucidating the Holy Teachings,” T31n1603) at 99.0% coverage, a verse summary of the prose treatise, itself a digest of a still larger work. This chain (T1579 → T1602 → T1603) illustrates how the Yogācāra scholastic tradition generated multi-layered textual hierarchies: a massive root treatise produces a prose digest, which in turn produces a verse compendium.

The significance of these results lies not in the individual identifications, most of which are known to specialists, but in the systematic quantification. Previous scholarship has described the *Yogācārabhūmi*’s role as a “mother text” in qualitative terms; the pipeline provides precise coverage measurements that rank the degree of textual dependence across the entire derivative network and reveal the layered structure of Yogācāra scholastic composition.

5.8 Chan/Zen Literature in Transmission Records

The pipeline reveals a distinctive pattern of text reuse in Chan (禪 *Chán*) literature, centered on the genre of transmission records (燈錄 *dēnglù*, “lamp records”). These compilations, which purport to record the lineage and sayings of Chan patriarchs and masters, turn out to be as much assemblages of prior textual material as original compositions.

The 景德傳燈錄 *Jǐngdé chuándēnglù* (“Record of the Transmission of the Lamp of the Jingde Era,” T51n2076), compiled by Daoyuan (道原 *Dàoyuán*) in 1004 CE, serves as the source for 8 derivative texts. The most striking are complete absorptions: the 信心銘 *Xìnxīn míng* (“Inscription on Faith in Mind,” T48n2010), attributed to the Third Patriarch Sengcan (僧璨 *Sēngcàn*), appears at 100% coverage within the 景德傳燈錄 *Jǐngdé chuándēnglù*. The 永嘉證道歌 *Yǒngjiā zhèngdào gē* (“Song of Enlightenment of Yongjia,” T48n2014), attributed to Yongjia Xuanjue (永嘉玄覺 *Yǒngjiā Xuánjué*), matches at 99.1%. The 黃檗山斷際禪師傳心法要 *Huángbò shān Duànjiè chánshī chuánxīn fǎyào* (“Essentials of Mind Transmission by Chan Master Duanji of Mount Huangbo,” T48n2012A) shows 54.4%, and various Chan masters’ recorded sayings (T47n1991, T47n1989, T47n1990, T47n1986B, T47n1986A) range from 32% to 52%.

Even more encyclopedic is the 宗鏡錄 *Zōngjìnglù* (“Records of the Mirror of the Source,” T48n2016), compiled by Yongming Yanshou (永明延壽 *Yǒngmíng Yánshòu*) in 961 CE. This massive 100-fascicle work absorbs material from 24 detected source texts, spanning Yogācāra treatises, Huayan (華嚴 *Huāyán*) doctrinal works, and Chan literature. Representative coverage levels include T46n1927 (80.4%), T19n1020 (65.9%), T46n1920 (62.2%), T31n1586 (55.2%), T32n1667 (46.2%), T45n1858 (40.9%), and the 永嘉證道歌 *Yǒngjiā zhèngdào gē* (T48n2014, 31.8%), the last showing that the same verse text was absorbed independently into both the 景德傳燈錄 *Jǐngdé chuándēnglù* and the 宗鏡錄 *Zōngjìnglù*.

These results provide computational confirmation of a point made by McRae (McRae 2003): Chan transmission records are compilations as much as original compositions, weaving together earlier textual material (poems, sayings, doctrinal treatises) into a narrative framework of lineage and transmission. The pipeline quantifies this compilatory dimension: when the 景德傳燈錄 *Jǐngdé chuándēnglù* contains the 信心銘 *Xìnxīn míng* at 100% coverage, the “transmis-

sion record” is functioning not as a record of oral teaching but as a textual anthology. The 宗鏡錄 *Zōngjìnglù*, with its 24 absorbed sources spanning multiple doctrinal traditions, reveals the full extent of Chan encyclopedic ambition, a synthetic project that rivals the Tang-dynasty encyclopedias discussed in §5.2 in its scope of textual incorporation.

6 Discussion

6.1 The Translator-Specific Matching Differential

The Heart Sūtra validation reveals a systematic feature of character-level text-reuse detection in translated corpora: the coverage measured depends heavily on whether the digest and its source were rendered by the same translator. The Kumārājīva Heart Sūtra (T250) shows 73.2% coverage against Kumārājīva’s own *Prajñāpāramitā* translation (T223), while the Xuanzang Heart Sūtra (T251) shows only 44.6% against the same T223, a 28.6-percentage-point gap despite both texts deriving from the same underlying material.

This gap quantifies a phenomenon well known qualitatively: each translator developed a consistent Chinese vocabulary for rendering Buddhist technical terms, and these vocabularies differed substantially across translators and eras. Kumārājīva (344–413 CE) and Xuanzang (602–664 CE) represent two of the most distinctive translation styles in the history of Chinese Buddhism. The 28.6-point differential provides a computational measure of their stylistic distance.

The implication for text-reuse detection is significant: coverage thresholds are effectively tuned for same-translator relationships, and cross-translator digest relationships are likely systematically underdetected. Texts classified as “shared tradition” at 20% cross-translator coverage might qualify as digests if the translator factor were controlled for.

6.2 Phonetic Transliteration Detection

The phonetic detection module identified 270 text pairs containing 990 individual phonetic match segments, i.e., passages where different Chinese characters encode the same Sanskrit sounds.

The strongest results come from the Mahāvairocana Sūtra cluster (T18n0848), where six of seven excerpt/digest derivatives show non-zero phonetic coverage, with phonetic-to-total coverage ratios reaching 18.5% (T18n0853). The Great Compassion Dhāraṇī recensions (T19n0974 family) reach 22–24%. These represent systematic transliteration variation across different renderings of the same mantra.

A unique case is T20n1111 from T20n1112, which has zero exact character overlap but 13.9% phonetic coverage, a relationship entirely invisible to character-level matching.

However, phonetic matching has modest impact on classification: only 10 relationships across the entire corpus change classification when phonetic matching is removed. It is best understood as a supplementary enrichment revealing transliteration variation within established relationships, rather than a primary discovery mechanism.

A fundamental challenge is that many common Buddhist Chinese vocabulary items double as phonetic transliteration characters. Characters like 菩 *pú* (*bodh-*), 般 *bō* (*praj-*), and 三 *sān* (*sam-*) appear thousands of times in a *Prajñāpāramitā* text in their semantic roles (as parts of 菩薩 *púsà* “bodhisattva,” 般若 *bōrě* “*prajñā*,” 三昧 *sānmèi* “*samādhi*”), but they are also in the transliteration table because the same characters are used phonetically elsewhere. The density-based region detector (which flags 20-character windows where 60% or more of characters are

in the transliteration table) therefore produces false positives: in T223 (285,968 characters, containing virtually no actual dhāraṇī material), 1.9% of the text is flagged as transliteration. The ambiguity filter (§3) mitigates this substantially: without it, the false-positive rate rises to 65%.

6.3 Independent Validation via Tibetan Parallels

To validate the pipeline’s retranslation detection, I compiled a unified cross-canon concordance merging nine independent catalog and scholarly data sources, covering 878 Taishō texts with Tibetan and/or Pāli parallels. The concordance is described in detail in a companion paper (Zigmond 2026).

Of the 224 detected retranslation pairs, 88 (39.3%) are independently confirmed by sharing at least one Tohoku or Otani catalog number in the Tibetan canon (Figure 4). Among pairs where both texts have Tibetan parallel data, the validation rate is 93.6%, strongly supporting the pipeline’s accuracy. The remaining 6.4% (6 pairs) are not necessarily errors: the Tibetan canon has its own retranslation tradition (སྐ་རྒྱུར *snga ’gyur* “old translation” vs. ཕྱི་རྒྱུར *phyi ’gyur* “new translation”), and the same Indic source may have been translated into Tibetan more than once.

Figure 4: Retranslation validation via the Tibetan parallel concordance. Of 224 detected retranslation pairs, 94 have Tibetan parallel data for both texts. Among these, 93.6% are independently confirmed by shared Tohoku or Otani catalog numbers.

6.4 The Shared Tradition Category

The 2,174 shared tradition relationships (10–30% overlap) represent texts sharing common Buddhist vocabulary without evidence of direct derivation. About 40% have coverage between 10–15%, barely above the minimum threshold. This category should be understood as a catch-all for low-level textual similarity; for analyses focused on direct textual relationships, it can be excluded.

7 Limitations

7.1 Character-Level Matching

The pipeline operates primarily at the character level, detecting verbatim or near-verbatim overlap supplemented by phonetic equivalence for transliterated passages. It cannot detect

paraphrase-level reuse, structural borrowing, or conceptual dependence without verbal overlap. Cross-translator digest relationships remain systematically underdetected for prose.

7.2 Directionality

The pipeline assumes the shorter text is the digest and the longer text is the source. This is a reasonable default but not always correct: short original sūtras may have been incorporated into later compilations (the Āgama extract cases illustrate this). Chronological direction cannot be determined from textual overlap alone.

7.3 False Positive Risks

Buddhist texts share extensive stock phrases even after stop-gram filtering. Two structural patterns, illustrated in Figure 5, can produce false positives.

First, encyclopedic compilations may create *transitive* false positives: if text A matches the 法苑珠林 *Fǎyuàn zhūlín* (T2122), which itself quotes text B, the pipeline reports an apparent A–B relationship that is actually mediated through the encyclopedia. Second, two texts may *independently* derive from a common Indic source that was never translated into Chinese (or whose Chinese translation is lost), producing shared content that reflects parallel transmission rather than direct textual borrowing within the Chinese tradition.

Figure 5: Two sources of false positives. (a) Transitive: an encyclopedia mediates an apparent relationship between two texts that have no direct connection. (b) Common source: two independent Chinese translations of the same Indic original share content through parallel transmission, not direct borrowing.

7.4 Phonetic Detection Limitations

The phonetic transliteration detection module, while capable of identifying cross-transliterator relationships invisible to character-level methods, suffers from false positives in transliteration region detection: in T223 (285,968 characters of *Prajñāpāramitā* prose with virtually no dhāraṇī content), 1.9% of the text is flagged as transliteration because common Buddhist vocabulary items like 菩 *pú* and 般 *bō* double as transliteration characters (without the ambiguity filter, this rises to 65%). The performance cost is also significant: phonetic rescan of novel segments adds substantial runtime, and for large pairs phonetic matching can consume up to 87% of total alignment time. The `PHONETIC_SEED_LENGTH` parameter of 5 may miss legitimate shorter matches, such as 2–3 character proper name variants that use different transliteration characters across translators. Despite these costs, only 10 relationships across the entire corpus change classification when phonetic matching is removed, suggesting that the module’s marginal contribution to classification accuracy is modest relative to its computational expense.

7.5 Genre-Specific Threshold Issues

The pipeline applies a single fixed threshold (30%) to distinguish digests from shared tradition across all genres. This uniform approach simplifies the methodology but does not account for the different textual characteristics of Buddhist literary genres (Table 7).

Table 7: Genre-specific behavior near the 30% digest threshold.

Genre (volumes)	Near threshold	With phonetic	Concern
Tantra (18–21)	124	20 (16%)	Transliterated content inflates coverage
Mahāyāna (9–17)	184	10 (5%)	Cross-translator pairs may fall below threshold

Note: “Near threshold” counts pairs with 25–35% coverage. “With phonetic” counts pairs where phonetic matching contributed to coverage.

Dhāraṇī texts (Taishō volumes 18–21) behave fundamentally differently from prose: their transliterated content is simultaneously “matching” (when the same transliteration characters are used) and “novel” (when different characters encode the same Sanskrit sounds). Of the 124 tantra pairs near the classification threshold, 16% have phonetic coverage that may artificially inflate their scores. Conversely, stock Buddhist phrases such as 如是我聞 *rúshì wǒ wén* (“Thus have I heard”) and 菩薩摩訶薩 *púsà móhēsà* (“bodhisattva mahāsattva”) constitute a larger proportion of short texts, so a 200-character text may share more formulaic overlap as a percentage than a 200,000-character one. The 30% threshold may therefore be too low for dhāraṇī-heavy volumes (where transliterated material inflates coverage) and too high for cross-translator prose digests (where the translator-specific matching differential documented in §6.1 suppresses it).

7.6 Shared Tradition Noise

The 2,174 shared tradition relationships constitute 60% of all detected relationships, and their interpretation requires caution. Approximately 40% have coverage between 10–15%, barely above the minimum threshold. This category should be interpreted honestly: it represents texts sharing common Buddhist vocabulary and formulaic phrasing, not direct derivation or deliberate textual reuse. For scholarly use, the higher-confidence categories (excerpt, digest, retranslation, and commentary, totaling 1,436 relationships) are substantially more reliable. Users of the pipeline’s output should consider filtering shared tradition pairs or treating them as hypothesis-generating rather than evidence-bearing (cf. Jockers 2013; Moretti 2013).

8 Future Directions

8.1 Paraphrase-Level Detection

The next frontier beyond character-level matching is paraphrase-level detection. Neural embeddings, whether at the sentence level or passage level, could detect cross-translator relationships where the same doctrinal idea is expressed in entirely different Chinese. The 28.6-percentage-point translator gap between Kumārājīva and Xuanzang (Section 6.1) demonstrates the ceiling of character-level methods: nearly a third of genuine textual overlap is invisible when the translator differs. Embedding-based methods trained on parallel Buddhist texts could close this gap, potentially reclassifying hundreds of shared tradition pairs as genuine digests or retranslations.

8.2 Chronological Ordering

The pipeline currently treats the shorter text as the derivative, a reasonable heuristic but not always correct. External metadata from the 開元釋教錄 *Kāiyuán shìjiào lù* (T2154) catalog dates, translator biographical data, and colophon information could add directionality to detected relationships. With chronological data, transitive relationships could be resolved (if A derives from B and B from C, then A's ultimate source is C) and compilation timelines could be mapped, tracing how material flowed from early translations into later encyclopedic compilations and back out as independent extracts.

8.3 Multi-Canon Extension

Extending the pipeline to cross-canon detection (comparing Tibetan Kangyur texts to Taishō parallels at the content level, rather than relying solely on catalog matching) would enable the identification of textual relationships that no concordance records. This would require cross-script alignment methods, possibly leveraging parallel Sanskrit fragments as pivot texts. The same approach could be applied to Pāli-Chinese detection, identifying cases where Chinese translations derive from Pāli sources rather than the usually assumed Sanskrit originals (cf. Nattier 1992).

8.4 Phonetic Refinement

Restricting phonetic source indexing to XML-annotated dhāraṇī ranges rather than scanning full texts would reduce Stage 3 runtime dramatically, eliminating the false-positive burden documented in Section 6.2. A Cython implementation of phonetic inner loops, currently the computational bottleneck for large dhāraṇī pairs, would provide an additional constant-factor speedup. More ambitiously, semantic phonetic matching that allows partial syllable similarity (e.g., *ga* matching *gha*, or *ta* matching *da*) could capture the systematic phonological correspondences between different transliteration traditions.

8.5 Community Validation

A web interface where scholars could confirm, reject, or annotate detected relationships would transform the pipeline from a one-time analysis into a living scholarly resource. Integration with CBETA's TEI apparatus would enable inline annotation of detected matches. Publishing the full results dataset (all 3,610 relationships with alignment details, coverage scores, and phonetic match data) for community review and extension would allow domain experts to evaluate the pipeline's classifications against their specialized knowledge. Such collaborative validation is essential for moving from computational detection to philological consensus (cf. Jockers 2013).

9 Conclusion

This study presents the first corpus-wide computational analysis of text reuse in the Chinese Buddhist canon, detecting 3,610 relationships across 1,558 texts. The results provide systematic evidence for patterns of textual transmission that have been described qualitatively but never quantified at scale: the absorption of hundreds of texts into encyclopedic compilations, the derivation of independent sūtras from Āgama collections, the network structure of dhāraṇī literature, and the measurable effect of translator identity on character-level overlap.

Taken together, these findings reveal the Taishō canon not as a collection of independent works but as a densely interconnected literary system shaped by centuries of compilation, extraction, and reuse. Tang-dynasty encyclopedists absorbed hundreds of shorter texts, sometimes nearly verbatim; compilers of sūtras drew selectively from longer sources, assembling new wholes from existing parts; and translators left identifiable stylistic signatures even when working from the same Indic originals. The 28.6-percentage-point gap between same-translator and cross-translator coverage points to a substantial layer of textual reuse that remains invisible to character-level methods, awaiting future approaches that can bridge differences in translation vocabulary.

Although developed for the Taishō, the pipeline is corpus-agnostic. Its only language-specific component is the character-to-syllable transliteration table; the fingerprinting, seed-and-extend alignment, and classification stages operate on any sufficiently digitized textual tradition. The same architecture could be applied to text reuse in the Pāli canon, the Tibetan Kangyur and Tengyur, Greek and Latin patristics, or classical Chinese secular literature, wherever digest composition, encyclopedic absorption, and retranslation have shaped a corpus. What the Taishō supplies is an unusually severe stress test: a logographic script with no word boundaries, multiple translators rendering the same Indic sources, and transliterated mantra that defeats character-level matching. A method robust to those conditions should transfer readily to alphabetic corpora, where the problem is comparatively constrained.

The pipeline was validated against the Heart Sūtra, the best-studied digest in the Chinese canon, and independently confirmed via Tibetan parallel data. All data and source code are publicly available.¹ By making the full catalog of detected relationships available for scholarly scrutiny, I hope to provide a foundation for new investigations into the transmission history, editorial practices, and intertextual architecture of one of the world's great literary collections.

¹The pipeline comprises approximately 5,900 lines of Python and 250 lines of Cython (compiled to C). Output data include the full relationship catalog (1.4 MB JSON, 3,610 entries) and per-pair alignment details (1.5 GB). Source code and results: <https://github.com/dangerzig/taisho-canon>.

A Technical Parameters

Table 8: Pipeline parameters.

Parameter	Value	Description
N-gram size	5	Character n-gram size
Stop-gram doc freq	0.05	Exclude n-grams in $>5\%$ of texts
Min containment	0.10	Minimum containment for candidate
Min size ratio	2.0	Source $\geq 2 \times$ digest
Max digest length	50,000	Maximum digest character count
Min seed length	5	Minimum exact match for seed
Fuzzy match score	+1	Character match reward
Fuzzy mismatch	-2	Mismatch/gap penalty
Fuzzy threshold	-4	Score drop to terminate
Excerpt threshold	0.80	Coverage for excerpt
Digest threshold	0.30	Coverage for digest
Shared tradition threshold	0.10	Minimum coverage
Retranslation ratio	3.0	Max ratio for retranslation
Commentary avg seg	10	Below this \rightarrow commentary
Phonetic seed length	5	Min phonetically equiv. chars
Phonetic n-gram size	3	Syllable n-gram size
Min phonetic containment	0.25	Phonetic containment threshold
Phonetic stopgram freq	0.05	Exclude syllable n-grams in $>5\%$
Phonetic max syllables	5	Ambiguity cap per character

Acknowledgments

The computational pipeline developed here relies on the CBETA digitization of the Taishō canon in TEI P5b XML format, without which corpus-wide analysis would not be possible. The cross-canon validation in §6.3 draws on Tibetan parallel data from SuttaCentral, 84000: Translating the Words of the Buddha, the rKTs project at the University of Vienna, and Lewis Lancaster’s *Korean Buddhist Canon* catalog. Charles Muller’s Digital Dictionary of Buddhism provided the phonetic transliteration data underlying the dhāraṇī detection module.

The author used Claude (Anthropic) as a coding assistant for the computational pipeline and data analysis scripts, and as an editing assistant during manuscript preparation. All scholarly judgments, interpretive claims, and responsibility for any errors are the author’s own.

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